

IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING LANGUAGE LINGUISTICALLY DIFFERENT STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10817146>

Claim to control intercultural groups has enlarged in the course of globalization and the subsequent formation of international organizations. Consequently, it is essential and applicable to arrange for a somewhat longer outline covering the wide field of intercultural teamwork.¹

Every classroom is a social community that reflects the disciplines, viewpoints, students, and the professor. It could be argued that effective learning involves an intercultural attitude where learners are liable for listening, reading and participating to understand both the viewpoints of classmates, writers, and faculty. Besides, they are responsible to understand their own viewpoints and how they acquired them. Students must understand that learning can be improved well as soon as it is done in a collaborative and non-competitive environment.

The multicultural classroom is the atmosphere forming several cultural, ethnic groups within one society. It can be a group of students in a school or university including people from different racial, historical and more importantly cultural background. More specifically, it can be defined as the family where parents come from very diverse nations (for example, Tajik-Uzbek, Arabic-Uzbek).

Preeti & Courtney stated that multicultural society is

1. the conservations of diverse cultures (cultural identities) in a unified society
2. numerous diverse cultures live together peacefully and impartially
3. in relation to social or educational theory that boosts importance in various cultures within a society rather than in only one ordinary culture.²

Caleb Rosado once defined multicultural classroom by responding a question “How can diversity be managed” as follows:

“Multicultural environment contains a system of views and manners that distinguishes and respects the existence of all different groups in an organization or society, recognizes and values their socio-cultural diversity and enables their continued support within a comprehensive cultural framework which authorizes all within the organization or society.”³

According to Caleb Rosado, multicultural environment is a “system,” a set of interrelated parts—in this case, views and manners—that make up the whole of how humans experience today’s world. It includes what people believe about others, their basic paradigms, and how this influences, and are impacted by manner. The outcome of this framework of views and manners are seven important actions.

The first is recognition of the rich diversity in a given society or organization. For the longest time racial/ethnic minorities, the physically disabled, and women have not been given the same

¹ M. Gallert, Teamwork, Team building, Team coaching. A practical guide to working in and with teams, p. 93.

² *Multiculturalism In the Classroom Presentation* By: Dan, Chris, Lisa, Jenny, Preeti & Courtney Slide 2 What is Multiculturalism?

³ Originally Published in Sumati Reddy, editor. Workforce Diversity, Vol. 3: Concepts and Cases. Hyderabad, India: ICAFAI University, p. 93

recognition as others. The one-sided approach to history and education has been a testimony to that fact.

With recognition also comes respect. Respect and recognition are not the same, since recognizing the existence of a group does not necessarily provoke respect for the group. In a slave society, for instance, the existence of slaves was recognized but their humanity was not respected. For example, in the USA, “whites” constantly recognized the presence of American Indians in the Western expansion of the continent, but their environmentally aware cultures were never respected. The contribution of women has usually been referred to a footnote status.

Multinational classroom also involves acknowledging the rationality of the cultural terms and influences of the different groups. It does not infer that all cultural contributions have equal value and social worth, or that all should be tolerated. Some cultural practices are better than others are for the overall improvement of society. These cultural expressions and contributions that differ from those of the dominant group in society are usually only acknowledged when there is an economic market for them, such as western music, native Uzbek dances for tourism or Korean cuisine. When there is a plan to maximize profit, the advertising industry depicts people of color in a positive light. However, in most other cases the entertainment media simply caricatures minority stereotypes, such as women usually in supportive roles. Multicultural society means to value what people have to offer, and not reject or depreciate it simply because it differs from the majority, or those in power, regard as important and valuable.

A person with another cultural background, for example, often involves discouragement because what they bring to discuss is often regarded as of little value. Not everything can be utilized, however, nor is of the same worth and value. Nevertheless, it does have value, even if for no other reason than the effort invested in bringing it forward. Such efforts must be encouraged, for who knows where the next great idea may come—from a youth, from an elderly person, from a single parent, from a high school dropout, from a business executive, or from rural part of a country?

Behind the concept of empowerment lies the process of enabling people to be self-critical of their own biases to strengthen themselves and others to achieve and arrange their maximum potential. People’s sense of self-worth, value and dignity is most often determined not only by the kind of support and encouragement they receive from others, but also from how willing they are to be self-examine negative behaviors in their own life and in their cultural group.

The principle of cultural diversity enables us to look upon the others that society has taught us to regard with distrust and suspicion, and to be taken advantage of, not as a “potential predator, but as a profitable partner.”

Another definition of cultural diversity is that within a comprehensive cultural framework many people get off and refuse to go along with an inclusive approach to society or to education. Many people fear diverse cultures and it will bring in “foreign” concepts and ideas, which will depart the nation from its historic course and transform the country into something different from what it has been.

Globalization is a social trend, which integrates people with different cultural backgrounds. Culture meet, clash, and grapple with each other as if in the contact zone.⁴ Under this

⁴www.pratt.edu

circumstance, people started to improve the teaching methods, which means the phenomenon of multicultural education is coming along with the development of globalization. The study of cultural diversity may bring both positive and negative sides influence to international students. It provides a relatively reasonable learning environment for international students, which can help them easier to get involved in a new community. In addition, with the help of this education method, international students can obtain more opportunities to better access to knowledge. Moreover, when teachers concentrate on developing the identity within multicultural classroom, it helps students with different cultural backgrounds progressively acquire global view.

Languages and the cultures that the local communities express and contain are becoming standardized according to Redman (2002) who argues, "English spans the divide between people and cultures. It is not owned by Britain and America: now it belongs to everyone".⁵ This may certainly mean that everybody belongs to English and other languages and cultural practices disappear and are lost forever. (Burnett, 2004)⁶

Most students require the lessons to be taught in English and Russian in Uzbekistan. In recent years, Uzbekistan is diversifying the tertiary education to be taught in English and some of the international institutions can be a very good example. Additionally, some universities require all the gradutors to do their theses in English.

Polylinguals.

Nevertheless can people speak more than one official language, most countries contain large numbers of people who use other languages. England uses one language for official languages; nevertheless, a survey of London found that 32 percent of children spoke languages other than English at home and that 300 different languages were spoken.⁷ Some countries, however, consist almost entirely of speakers of a single language: 99.3 percent of the inhabitants of Japan speak Japanese (Grosjean, 1982).⁸ Others keep a variety of languages under one official language. France has an estimated 9 million people who are bilingual in other indigenous languages, not taking into account 2 million migrant workers from Portugal and North Africa (Valdman, 1976; Harding and Riley, 1986);⁹ undoubtedly more bilinguals in Vancouver speak Chinese alongside English than French, despite English and French being the official languages. In the United States the population of over 17s in the 1990 was 150 million, of whom 21 million spoke other languages than English, i.e. one in seven according to the US Census Bureau (1996); this trend has led to a worry about the continuing status and importance of English.

Freedom of movement also has its impact on polylinguals. Some countries, for one historical reason or other, contain static residents of speakers of different languages, occasionally known as 'interior colonies'. The UK has had speakers of Welsh, Gaelic and English for many centuries. In the outskirts of Dublin, they teach Gaelic to very young children. They may not speak language much outside school, but their parents want them to be as bilingual as possible.

⁵ Redman, C (2002) "Wanna Speak English" Time Magazine, p.45

⁶ Swinburne, J (2003) "Some social and cultural issues of english as the global language: Everything Is Changing, Everything Is Going, Going", University of Technology, Lilydale Campus Australia, p. 237

⁷ Maurais, J & Morris, M A. "Languages in a globalizing world", Cambridge University, 2004, p. 62-78

⁸ Grosjean, F. (1982). Life with two languages: An introduction to bilingualism. Cambridge, MA.: Harvard University Press, p. 14-20

⁹ *Language in Society*, Vol. 16, No. 3 (Sep., 1987), Cambridge University Press, p. 440-448

The fact that teaching a foreign language cannot be effectively carried out without giving understanding of its culture has led to a very hard job for those involving the practice of the English language teaching. Educators may unintentionally have been inserting western culture in their classroom, while learners may have been learning western culture while learning the language. This condition may lead to the decrease of the future generations' understanding towards their own culture. They may have been internalizing the foreign culture in their life, and becoming strangers of their own culture. This will not be beneficial for the sustainability of the country considering the fact that education may be regarded as an investment in human capital formation. This particular study, however, focuses on three main issues concerning the practice of English language teaching in relation to maintaining the nation identity.

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